

Reviewer 4:

Thank you for appreciating our work. We tried to provide sufficient reasons for addressing fairness in the paper. If the timeouts for servers shoot or diminish highly, the elections can take forever to complete, as described in Section 6D. However, our results from Figures 7 and 8 show that we are able to complete elections and reduce the number of terms between successive elections as compared to Vanilla Raft. We also provide reasons why the phase2 of our algorithm is fair. Thus, fairness should not be a concern for our algorithm. If required, we can definitely add a formal argument addressing these in our camera-ready version.

For the second feedback, our algorithm focuses on developing an “understanding” between servers of any given distributed system as the time passes, and that’s why we introduce the booting phase. The servers develop more and more understanding as the time passes, longer the time, better the results. More data from past elections will definitely help develop greater understanding amongst the servers. So, even if the dynamics of the distributed system change after it stays online for a long time, it will only benefit our algorithm by providing more data.

We hope we have addressed your concerns sufficiently and any upgrades to our score will be really helpful.